

Deliverable D-WP5.2 – Development of a national One Health surveillance roadmap ¹

OHEJP JIP MATRIX – WP 5

Responsible Partner: 41-SVA

Contributing partners: 9-BfR, 21-APHA,
23-UoS, 27-ISS, 28-IZSAM, 30-RIVM, 32-FHI,
33-NVI, 34-PIWET, 40-FoHM, 13-SSI

¹ Original title: OHS roadmap template document

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
Funding	This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 773830.
Grant Agreement	Grant agreement n° 773830
Start Date	01/01/2018
Duration	60 Months

DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

Title OHEJP deliverable	D-WP5.2 – Development of a national One Health surveillance roadmap – Original title: OHS roadmap template document		
WP and task	WP5-T2 – Develop a national OH surveillance roadmap template		
Leader	41-SVA		
Other contributors	9-BfR, 21-APHA, 23-UoS, 27-ISS, 28-IZSAM, 30-RIVM, 32-FHI, 33-NVI, 34-PIWET, 40-FoHM, 13-SSI		
Due month of the deliverable	M58		
Actual submission month	M58		
Type <i>R: Document, report</i> <i>DEC: Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.; OTHER</i>	R, DEC Save date: 1-Dec-22		
Dissemination level <i>PU: Public (default)</i> <i>CO: confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services).</i>	PU		
Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Communication Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/> National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/> EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EEA <input type="checkbox"/> EMA <input type="checkbox"/> FAO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WHO <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OIE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other international stakeholder(s): as per OHJEP dissemination plans Social Media: n.a. Other recipient(s): n.a.		

ONE HEALTH SURVEILLANCE ROADMAP TEMPLATE DOCUMENT

Table of contents

Background	4
1. Introduction	4
1.1. MATRIX.....	4
1.2. Work package 5 – task 2 (WP5-T2).....	4
MATRIX contributions to the roadmap	5
1. Pilots in Sweden and Denmark.....	5
1.1. Pilot description: Salmonella surveillance and control in Sweden	5
1.2. Pilot description: OHS in Denmark.....	6
2. MATRIX solutions on the OHRAS	8
2.1. Barriers to OHS	8
2.2. OH EpiCap tool for evaluation.....	8
2.3. OHS Interactive guide	8
2.4. Common OHS framework	8
2.5. OHS Dashboard Information Centre	8
2.6. Glossary	9
2.7. OHS Codex – Knowledge Information Platform (KIP)	9
Webinar series – Solutions for OHS in Europe	9
New version of OHRAS – timeline for publication of new material	9

Background

1. Introduction

1.1. MATRIX

MATRIX is a project of the [One Health European Joint Programme \(OHEJP\)](#), a partnership of 44 food, veterinary and medical laboratories and institutes across Europe and the [Med-Vet-Net Association](#). MATRIX connects existing cross-sectorial One Health programmes in European countries. Today, 19 partner institutes representing the animal health (AH), public health (PH), and food safety (FS) sectors from 12 countries continue a collaboration that started early in 2020 and will end in December 2022. More information can be found [here](#).

The purpose of MATRIX is to create practical solutions for European countries to support and to advance the implementation of One Health Surveillance (OHS). This is done by creating synergies between the different sectors at the national level. While other OHEJP projects focused on implementing OHS at the end of the surveillance continuum in each sector, MATRIX aims to strengthen OHS along the entire surveillance pipeline, from implementation to output. MATRIX focuses on building upon existing resources, rather than developing new systems, to account for the unique infrastructural capacities of each country. In this report we describe the work of MATRIX WP5 task 2 “Develop a national OH surveillance roadmap template”, which was partly done in collaboration with the OHEJP Joint Integrative Project (JIP) COHESIVE.

1.2. Work package 5 – task 2 (WP5-T2)

The original task was described as creating a OHS roadmap template on the basis of the requirements and findings outlined in task 1 of WP5. The roadmap was intended to be a high-level strategic guide (similar to a checklist), outlining key elements needed for (future) national development of cross-sectorial and trans-disciplinary surveillance capacity. A change of this task was proposed (and approved by OHEJP WP4 in 2021) as follows:

This task will evaluate and further develop the roadmap that was built within the JIP COHESIVE project. The JIP COHESIVE roadmap focuses on One Health collaborations during risk analysis of zoonoses but also covers One Health surveillance (which is the focus of MATRIX and MATRIX WP5-T2).

The evaluation of the JIP COHESIVE roadmap will be performed by reviewing the guidelines and testing the structure of the webpage that was created by JIP COHESIVE. As part of the evaluation of the roadmap, national systems thinking workshops (with focus on one or more MATRIX-hazard tracks per country) will be performed, involving stakeholders and non-partners of MATRIX from OHEJP and beyond. Results from the requirement analysis of MATRIX WP5-T1 and MATRIX WP2-T2 will be compared with and incorporated into the guidelines of the existing roadmap. Also, important lessons learnt from the Hazards Tracks in MATRIX will be used to further develop the guidelines of the roadmap. Finally, the JIP COHESIVE website will be updated to integrate the work of MATRIX WP5-T2.

The deliverable of COHESIVE is directly in line with the original plans for the roadmap of MATRIX WP5-T2. Considering that it is more efficient and sustainable to build upon the experiences and work already performed within COHESIVE rather than develop a new tool, it was proposed to change the MATRIX WP5-T2 work plan to build upon the COHESIVE roadmap. By building upon the existing roadmap, MATRIX contributed to the evaluation and development of COHESIVE's work.

In order to inform the work with the roadmap, a requirement analysis was performed in WP5, task 1 (1). The requirement analysis consisted of three parts: a systematic literature review, collection of user stories, and an output review of relevant OHEJP projects and deliverables. More specifically, the literature review focused on collecting available evidence on existing barriers and facilitators to the

design, development, and implementation, including monitoring, of integrated OHS at country level in Europe. The user stories were collected from professionals and MATRIX colleagues working directly with OHS systems. This was done in the form of a workshop organized by MATRIX WP2-T2 (2). Main findings from the literature review and the user stories will be available on the OHRAS webpage. The output review of OHEJP projects resulted in a close collaboration with [COHESIVE](#), more specifically around the ongoing work with a webpage containing a roadmap for creating a One Health Risk Analysis System ([OHRAS](#) – copy-paste the link) (3).

MATRIX contributions to the roadmap

The content of the OHRAS webpage was reviewed by the MATRIX WP5-T2 working group before it was made publicly available at www.ohras.eu. The evaluation of the roadmap was done by following the guidelines and steps of the OHRAS.

1. Pilots in Sweden and Denmark

Sweden and Denmark used the information on the OHRAS webpage to evaluate the content and to improve the OHS work in each country. The first three steps of the roadmap were fulfilled by both countries and the Swedish group has made plans for continuation of their work.

Description of the pilots are available on the OHRAS in conjunction with the third steppingstone (systems mapping of the current situation) to provide users with examples of what other countries have done.

1.1. Pilot description: Salmonella surveillance and control in Sweden

1.1.1. Steppingstone 1: Set priority and goal

It was decided to focus on salmonella and more specifically salmonella control and surveillance in cattle and pigs in Sweden. In 2021, a government assignment to review, and if necessary, revise the Swedish salmonella control program was given jointly to the Swedish Board of Agriculture and the National Veterinary Institute. A mapping of the present program according to OHRAS was included in the review with the aim to identify challenges and investigate if the suggested updates and revisions would address these challenges.

1.1.2. Steppingstone 2: Stakeholder analysis

The core group consisted of representatives from the National Veterinary Institute (SVA), the Public Health Agency of Sweden, the Swedish Board of Agriculture, and the Swedish Food Agency. The stakeholder analysis was performed online with the core group, six people in total. It worked well to have the discussion online, this is a good alternative when the members of the core group are located in different parts of the country. The Mendelow Matrix was used to categorize the stakeholders. Only stakeholders that ended up as having both a high interest and high power were invited to the workshop. It was decided not to invite more than 25-30 people to be able to have discussions with the whole group.

In addition to the core group, representatives from the following organizations were invited:

Lantbrukarnas Riksförbund (LRF) – The Federation of Swedish Farmers

Gård och Djurhälsan – Farm and Animal Health

Växa – Cattle farmers association

Distriktsveterinärerna – District veterinarians

Svenska köttföretagen – Swedish Meat Enterprises

County veterinary officers from four different counties

County medical officer

In total, there were 23 participants from 11 different organizations/authorities at the workshop.

In addition to the Swedish participants, Simon Rüegg (Zürich University) and Kitty Maassen (leader of the OHEJP COHESIVE) helped us organize and run the workshop.

1.1.3. Steppingstone 3: Systems mapping of the current situation

The purpose was to jointly map the components of the salmonella control program along the food chain from farm to fork where all sectors, organizations and actors were taken into account. The purpose was also to compare the current system with the new proposal for alternatives presented in the government assignment regarding salmonella management and monitoring of cattle and pigs in Sweden. Separate maps for cattle and pigs were to be created at first and then be compared to look at what differences there are. Questions to discuss: What are the pros and cons with the current system? How would a change affect different actors?

What were the outcomes of the workshop?

The workshop was held as a physical meeting in Uppsala over 1,5 days, ending with lunch the second day. No online option was given as the format of this workshop is not suitable for online or hybrid solutions. The interaction between people was very valuable both during group activities at the tables or by the whiteboard and also for discussions with the whole group.

A major part of the first day was spent on introducing the participants to the concept of systems thinking. Exercises were held to help the participants understand this way of working. In the afternoon of the first day a mapping exercise was conducted, however a comprehensive map of the salmonella system was not produced due to shortage of time and also a lack of understanding.

The second day was spent on discussing challenges with the current system and links were created between perceived challenges and the new suggested/proposed changes (in the government assignment). Most challenges were being addressed in the proposed revision of the program, but some were not. Challenges were put forward and prioritized and it was made clear what the important questions and concerns for the participating organizations were. Although a comprehensive map of the system was not produced it was very valuable to list and discuss challenges (and to whom it was a challenge, and what effect it would have on different actors).

What is the next step?

All material from the workshop (white board and notes) was digitalised and summarised for future use. Listed challenges were grouped into three major areas and stakeholders were grouped according to their specific interest and knowledge of the three areas to facilitate more in-depth discussion. Next step will be to meet physically in these smaller groups to have a more detailed analysis of dependencies and challenges within these areas.

Some reflections

The groups ran out of time the first day when they were mapping the current system of salmonella control in Sweden. They could have spent less time on the introduction to systems thinking and more time on the actual exercises about the salmonella system. They did not have time to make different maps for cattle and pigs as planned. The participants were a bit frustrated that they did not get enough time to discuss during the first day. A lesson learned is that it is valuable to have plenty of time for discussion, especially if you invite a large group of people from many different organizations. The concept of systems thinking, and the exercises were all introduced in English and because there were a lot of new terminology this was sometimes perceived as a barrier. To save time it is a good idea to have a few participants in the workshop that is familiar with systems thinking that can guide the groups (one per table) in their preferred language.

1.2. Pilot description: OHS in Denmark

1.2.1. Steppingstone 1: Set priority and goal

The aims of the workshop included:

- Making an overall surveillance map to ensure a shared understanding of OHS in Denmark
- Highlighting strengths and weaknesses in order to optimize OHS

- Discussing desires for the system in the future
- Introducing participants across sectors and backgrounds to the systems thinking concept

The core group involved 4-5 people involved in One Health at Statens Serum Institut (SSI). Rather than choosing one hazard of focus for the workshop, the core group decided to design the workshop in a way that allowed participants to work with any zoonotic agent that was relevant and interesting to them within the FS sector and/or at the AH/PH interface.

1.2.2. Steppingstone 2: Stakeholder analysis

The core group carried out a stakeholder analysis using the Mendelow matrix. Agencies and institutes directly related to the surveillance of zoonoses within the PH, FS and AH sectors across institutes were prioritized. The core group decided to exclude industry actors at this workshop. It would be relevant to include the industry when working with surveillance systems where industry actors play a role, which is something that could be done in future workshops.

All invitations to the systems thinking workshop were sent via email to publicly available contact lines for each of the identified stakeholders. This was done to ensure that the invitations were not limited to people already known to the system, thus trying to expand and integrate all relevant stakeholders to these issues.

1.2.3. Steppingstone 3: Systems mapping of the current situation

The zoonotic agents participants elected to work with at the workshop included avian and swine influenza, rabies, psittacosis and to different *Salmonella* spp.

For each of these six zoonotic agents, participants used systems thinking to map their understanding of the current surveillance system in place, resulting in six different surveillance maps. Due to the similarities, both in surveillance map and nature of pathogen, between avian and swine influenza, rabies and psittacosis, and the two *Salmonella* spp., the six groups were merged into three, and three new maps were created: one for influenza surveillance, one for zoonotic agents in the AH sphere, and salmonella surveillance. Then, based on these three maps, the entire workshop collaborated to create one, overall map of OH surveillance within Denmark.

The workshop was held in person over two days. Participants were asked not to bring their computers and no online option was offered, in order to encourage people to be more active and present. The in-person component was extremely important for the workshop as it allowed colleagues who work together but have never met to be in the same room and work on something engaging. Keeping lectures to a minimum and encouraging hands-on activities was also key to ensure that participants played an active role in the workshop. The workshop provided a great opportunity for networking as well as an introduction to systems thinking across many institutes, disciplines, and sectors. The workshop also highlighted complexity of the systems and aspects where participants were not necessarily in agreement.

As a part of the conclusion of the workshop, a list of actionable follow up items/strategies was created based upon the perspectives and experiences of the participant audience. Participants were asked to vote on which of the items they would prioritize moving forward. Further follow up has been difficult to carry out due to limited resources and prioritization from management. However, participants walked away from the workshop valuing systems thinking and its functionality within their own working groups and workflows. For future workshops, we recommend crafting a concrete plan to use the outcomes of the workshop immediately and more directly, with approval and support from management. Additionally, having the maps in a digital format would have helped to preserve them and share them with participants.

2. MATRIX solutions on the OHRAS

The roadmap was intended to make use of the work and solutions that were developed within MATRIX. Below is a brief description of the tools and guides that will be available on the OHRAS webpage by the end of 2022 when the updated version of the webpage is published. To make it easier for users that are primarily interested in OHS, a new tab called *OH Surveillance* will be introduced in the top menu of the webpage. This is where most of the MATRIX contributions will be located.

2.1. Barriers to OHS

On the OHRAS webpage under *More Information* is a section about barriers to setting up a OH risk analysis system. As previously mentioned, a systematic literature review was performed in MATRIX WP5-T1 investigating barriers to OHS (1), more specifically regarding the design, development, and implementation, including monitoring of integrated OHS at the national level in Europe. The main factors that stand in the way of the practical implementation of a OHS system were described. This information can be used to advise surveillance actors how to circumvent barriers that prevent efficient OHS and to value facilitators that support it. The text about OHS barriers will be available under the *OH Surveillance* tab on the OHRAS webpage.

2.2. OH EpiCap tool for evaluation

The [OH EpiCap tool](#) (4) was developed within WP4 of MATRIX. It is an interactive evaluation tool for One Health epidemiological surveillance capacities and capabilities. It can be used to evaluate a specific sector and/or pathogen of choice. Additionally, the tool allows for benchmarking of surveillance capacities and capabilities. This tool can be used as a first step of the roadmap, to help prioritize areas that need improvements before setting the priority and goal (steppingstone 1). It can also be used in later stages of the roadmap. A link to the tool and a description will be provided on the OHRAS webpage under the *OH Surveillance* tab.

2.3. OHS Interactive guide

This [interactive guide](#) was developed within WP1 of MATRIX (5). It is designed to support users in creating a OHS system from already existing surveillance programs in different sectors. It can be used as a standalone tool or in conjunction with the OHRAS roadmap. The guide can be used at the fourth steppingstone as an alternative approach for people specifically working with OHS development. A link to the guide and a description will be provided on the OHRAS webpage under the *OH Surveillance* tab.

2.4. Common OHS framework

The common OHS framework is a general template for users to refer to when looking to design and develop a OHS system. The common OHS framework is based on a summary of the surveillance chain maps performed in WP2 of MATRIX (2) across sectors (AH, PH and FS) in eight European countries for four pathogens. A high-level summary of similarities and shared structures in place in OHS systems in various countries, across different hazards is presented in a graphic illustration. The framework provides the user with an overview of how these systems are structured within Europe. This information will be provided on the OHRAS webpage under the *OH Surveillance* tab.

2.5. OHS Dashboard Information Centre

This is an [information centre](#) with a practical manual for the development of interactive dashboards for One Health surveillance in Europe, and an inventory of existing dashboards. It was produced within WP6 of MATRIX. A dashboard is a form of graphical user interface which displays data and metrics in a way that facilitates tracking, analysis, and monitoring to inform decision-making. A disease surveillance dashboard might contain charts, tables, maps, or other elements providing a comprehensive overview of the development of the disease in question, or even predicting future outbreak events. The dashboards, which can include surveillance data from all relevant sectors can be used by surveillance officials in PH, AH and FS. These types of OH dashboards can be relevant for the

OH Activity *Signalling*, which is described as follows on the OHRAS webpage: *Signalling - Sharing information on events or trends at an early stage with relevant parties across sectors*. A description and a link to the dashboard information centre will be available on the OHRAS website under the *OH Surveillance* tab and under *OH Activities – Signalling – Tools*.

2.6. Glossary

A glossary for the OHRAS webpage will be created by using the OHEJP [Glossaryfication Service](#). The OHEJP Glossary was developed as a joint effort between JIP ORION, JIP COHESIVE, and JRP NOVA projects. The glossary will be available on the OHRAS webpage under the *More Information* tab.

2.7. OHS Codex – Knowledge Information Platform (KIP)

The OHS [Codex/KIP](#) is a framework that helps establish and strengthen inter-institutional collaboration and transdisciplinary knowledge transfer in the area of surveillance data integration and interpretation, along the OH objective of improving health and well-being. The OHS Codex/KIP has been designed in such a way, that it can act as a resource itself, i.e., it provides a collection of methods, tools, and resources that could be used or customized by interested institutions. Compared to the guidance available in the [Tripartite Zoonoses Guide](#) the OHS Codex/KIP focus on the needs of national European institutions. It has also been designed as a living document, so that it can be updated continuously. This work was carried out within the frame of the JIP ORION project. Based upon the foundation laid out by ORION, MATRIX continued this work (6). A link and a description will be available on the OHRAS webpage under *More Information - Tools*.

Webinar series – Solutions for OHS in Europe

As part of the sustainability strategy of MATRIX, a webinar series about solutions for OHS in Europe ([webinar invitation](#)) was arranged during 2022. A joint webinar about the roadmap was held together with COHESIVE in October. The initial work by COHESIVE was presented as well as the pilots in Sweden and Denmark, and the new material that MATRIX will contribute to the OHRAS webpage. There were approximately 30 participants (including presenters) from 17 countries attending the webinar.

New version of OHRAS – timeline for publication of new material

Adding and updating pages on the OHRAS webpage (www.ohras.eu) is still a work in progress as per writing this deliverable (October 2022). A new section for OHS has been created and new material has been added and incorporated into the COHESIVE roadmap and guidelines. The plan is to publish the new version of the OHRAS webpage in December 2022, before the end of MATRIX.

Bibliography

1. Eves C, Friesema I, Skjerdal OT, Holmberg M, Ågren E, Lopez de Abechuco E, Daugaard Larsen H, Kjær Lefèvre S, Benedetti G, Partner R, et al. Deliverable D-JIP-MATRIX-WP5.1 - Report on requirement analysis for "OHS roadmap template." (2022). 1–34 p. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6504418>
2. Cito F, Amato L, Ågren E, Holmberg M. Deliverable D-JIP-MATRIX-WP2.1 MAPPING OF THE SURVEILLANCE CHAIN FOR ALL HAZARD TRACKS, AND CROSS-SECTORIAL LINKAGES. (2022). 1–57 p. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6406150>
3. COHESIVE. (2021). Deliverable D-JIP2-D2.5 Development of common procedures and tools (COHESIVE) (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5801882>
4. Viviane Henaux, Henok Tegegne, Carlijn Bogaardt, Renaud Lailler, Lucie Collineau, & Joaquin Prada. (2022). Deliverable D-JIP-MATRIX-WP4.2 OH-EpiCap tool and tutorial. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7006654>
5. Johanna Dups-Bergmann, & Carola Sauter-Louis. (2022). Deliverable D-JIP-MATRIX-WP1.2 Description of a common framework for One Health surveillance. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7064374>
6. Esther M. Sundermann, & Estibaliz Lopez de Abechuco. (2021). MILESTONE M-WP5.1 "KNOWLEDGE-PLATFORM OPERATIONAL". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5175982>